

**PHYTOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS OF
VALERIANA OFFICINALIS L. IN THE CONDITIONS OF TASHKENT
OASIS.**

Termiz davlat universiteti talabalari

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Abstract: This article investigated that the phyto-chemical content of on and underground parts of herb called Valeriana was found in plants planted during vegetation periods in spring and autumn.

Key words: phyto-chemical, introduction, morphology, penology, productivity, agrotechnology,

Introduction.

In traditional agriculture to recognize the importance of process of introduction and climate settings of herbs is dependent on the knowledge of their phyto-chemical gradient.

Valeriana officinalis L., included in the family of Valerianaceae, is a several-year-living plant with 60-150 cm tall. It mainly grows in wet ground, grasslands, on the shore of rivers and bushlands. Naturally it is found in Eastern Europe, Russia, Belorussia, Ukraine, Moldova and the Caucasus.[1]

In the medicine the herbal valeriana's preparations is considered to be one of the primary means to cure heart diseases and calm neuro-system (in sleeplessness and other neurological disorders).

Research methods: Separation of essential oils from plants was carried out on the basis of Ginzberg(1987) busle by hydrodistillation by Klevenger and driving of essential oils GF SSSR XI [2]

The photochemical composition of plants was determined jointly with the staff of the Department of Pharmacognosy of the Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute.

Research results.

We conducted our scientific research under Tashkent climate with in-autumn-planted herbs. In the first vegetation period on the ground the percentages of efir oil and acid isovaleriana were 0.25% and 0.78%, respectively, while those under the ground showed 0.33% of efir and 1.34% of acid isovaleriana. vegetatioin the second vegetation period the numbers were 0.30% and 1.18% on the ground and 0.36% and 1.53% under, respectively. These findings revealed that in spring plants

Table 1

Phytochemical composition of medicinal valerian

Planting time	Vegetation period	Surface parts		Underground parts	
		Essential oil %	Isovaleric acid %	Essential oil %	Isovaleric acid %
Autumn	1	0,25	0,78	0,33	1,34
	2	0,30	1,18	0,36	1,53
Spring	1	0,23	0,71	0,24	1,18

	2	0,25	0,84	0,26	1,27
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Conclusions. Thus, the qualitative change in the phytochemical composition of surface and underground organs of plants sown in the autumn period, the early development of plants sown in the spring period and the length of the growing season and the coefficient of the average daily useful temperature.

References:

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